

National Evolutionary Synthesis Center

2024 W. Main St., Suite A200
Durham, NC 27705 USA
<http://www.nescent.org>
919-668-4551

3 June 2011 dw

LEADER'S CHECKLIST FOR GROUP MEETINGS

Immediate needs relevant to your award:

1. Your signed offer letter returned to NESCent with anticipated date of meeting (mail to Danielle Wilson, danielle@nescent.org)
2. Review the following documents
 - a. Informational Letter from Director
 - b. Staff Contacts
 - c. NESCent Travel Guidelines
 - d. IT Support Policy
 - e. Reporting Requirements
 - f. Best Practices (working groups only)
3. Contact Karen Cranston, Training Coordinator & Bioinformatics Project Manager (karen.cranston@nescent.org), to discuss informatics support

Due 4 months before meeting – logistical planning with NESCent coordinator;

Danielle Wilson (Danielle@nescent.org) or Stephanie Risbon (Stephanie@nescent.org):

1. Confirmation of meeting dates (or alternative dates)
2. Review NESCent standardized meeting format
3. Provide coordinator list of attendees, with their email addresses and home institutions

Due 3 months before meeting – logistical planning with NESCent coordinator:

1. Coordinator contacts all participants with travel arrangements and policies
2. Participants register for the meeting by entering demographic and reimbursement information into NESCent's administrative database (NEAD) at <https://nead.nescent.org>
 - ***Registration in NEAD is a pre-requisite for booking air travel***
3. Participants make airline reservations
4. Provide coordinator the science agenda

Due 1 month before meeting – logistical planning with NESCent coordinator:

1. Provide coordinator catering and meal preferences

Due 1 week before meeting – logistical planning with NESCent coordinator:

1. Coordinator sends to all participants the final agenda, list of participants, and arrival/departure information

Due 1 week after meeting:

1. Participants send receipts for reimbursements to Barbara Mitchell, 2024 W. Main St., Suite A200, Durham, NC 27705

Due 1 month after meeting:

1. Enter meeting report into the NESCent Administrative Database (NEAD) at <https://nead.nescent.org>
2. Select date for next meeting (working groups only)
3. One month and beyond, contact Robin Smith, Communications Manager (rsmith@nescent.org), about papers in press and other products you would like our news office to highlight.
4. Enter published papers and other products into NEAD.